

ANDRAGOGICA MODEL OF LEARNING

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Annotation: *The article examines the andragogical model of adult learning. Andragogy makes the following assumptions about the design of learning: adults need to know why they need to learn something, adults need to learn experientially, adults approach learning as problem-solving, and adults learn best when the topic is of immediate value.*

Keywords: *andragogy, adults, adult learning, pedagogy, psychology, knowledge, pattern of education.*

In modern conditions, the objective and subjective needs for training of a huge number of people are sharply increasing. According to one of the greatest theorists and practitioners of adult education, the American scientist M.Sh. Knowles, the main task today has become "the production of competent people - people who would be able to apply their knowledge in changing conditions, and whose main competence would be the ability to engage in constant self-training throughout their entire lives."

The emergence of andragogy – the science of adult education is – due to a number of different reasons: socio – economic , cultural, ecological and personal. In the second half of the 20th century, the entire sphere of education began to change significantly. The concepts of free learning and continuous education emerged. Advances in information transfer technology made it possible to organize the pedagogical process in a new way. The humanities came to the ideas of activity theory and “ humanistic” psychology. Philosophy came to the realization of the decisive role of man in his own destiny, in the destinies of the surrounding world. It helped to understand that man, although dependent on natural, economic and social conditions of existence, is able to build his own personality, a system of personal spiritual and moral values. Physiology and psychology have proven that people are capable of successfully learning practically throughout their entire conscious life. All these ideas helped to come to an understanding of the need to free a person from the strict school framework, helped them to acquire a leading role in the process of their learning. First of all, this concerned an adult. The final formation of the foundations of andragogy was carried out in the 1970s in the works of the outstanding American scientist M.Sh. Knowles, the Englishman P. Jarvis, the American R.M. Smith and a

group of young scientists from the University of Nottingham. In 1970, Malcolm Sheppard Knowles published a fundamental work on andragogy "Modern Practice of Adult Education" in which he formulated the main provisions of the new science.

Taking into account all the objective changes in the educational sphere and the achievements of various sciences in understanding the role of man in his life, these scientists proceeded from the fundamental differences between an adult and a non-adult person in general, and in the learning process, in particular. The main features of the adult learning process are:

1. The leading role in the learning process belongs to the learner.
2. The learner's desire for self-realization, independence, and self-management.
3. The presence of life (everyday, social, professional) experience in an adult, which can be used as an important source of learning for both him and his colleagues.
4. An adult learns to solve his important life problem and achieve a specific goal.
5. An adult expects immediate application of the skills, abilities, knowledge and qualities acquired during training.
6. The educational activity of a student is largely determined by time, space, everyday, professional and social factors that either limit or facilitate the learning process.
7. The process of adult learning is organized as a joint activity of the student and the teacher at all its stages: diagnostics, planning, implementation, evaluation and, to a certain extent, correction.

Based on the above, andragogy should be defined as the science of adult learning, substantiating the activities of learners and teachers in organizing and implementing the learning process. Like any science, andragogy has its own structure, conceptual and terminological apparatus. Since it reveals the general patterns of adult learning, it highlights the theory of adult learning. This section examines the most general categories: the characteristics of an adult learner, the process of adult learning, the relationship of andragogy with various areas of education. Andragogy studies and formulates the basic patterns of activity of students in the learning process and its integral part is the technology of teaching adults.

The main provisions of the theory of adult learning are best considered by comparing the pedagogical and andragogical models of learning. When we talk about a learning model, we mean a systematized set of basic patterns of the activities of the learner and the teacher in the learning process. At the same time, it is necessary to take into account other components of the process - the content, sources, means,

forms and methods of learning. But the main thing in the model is the activity of the learner and the teacher.

From an andragogic perspective, adult learners (as well as older adolescents in certain situations), who have a deep need for autonomy (although in some situations they may be temporarily dependent on someone), should play a leading role in the process of their education. The teacher's task is to encourage and support the development of adult self-management, to assist the learner in determining the parameters of learning and finding information.

From the point of view of the andragogical model, a person accumulates significant experience that can be used as a source of learning for both the learner and other people. The function of the teacher in this case is to help the learner identify the latter's experience. The main forms of classes are laboratory experiments, discussions, solving specific problems, and various types of business games. The readiness of students to learn is determined by their need to study something to solve specific problems, therefore, the student plays a leading role in the formation of motivation and determination of learning goals. The task of the teacher is to create favorable conditions for the student, provide him with the necessary methods and criteria that would help to clarify his needs. In this case, training programs should be built on the basis of their possible application in life; in this regard, the basis for organizing the process is the individualization of training, pursuing specific goals for each student.

In conclusion, it should be emphasized that andragogy is a science for people who are independent, self-sufficient, striving for self-realization in various spheres of activity, people for whom “it is necessary to learn in order to exist” and who realize that “human existence itself must be inextricably linked with learning.”

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